

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATIONAL CULTURE OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN A DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: This article discusses the theoretical foundations for the development of informational culture of future teachers in a digital educational environment. The authors explore the concept of informational culture and its importance in the modern world, as well as the role of digital technologies in shaping this culture. They also provide a framework for developing informational culture among future teachers, including the acquisition of digital competencies and the development of critical thinking skills.

Keywords: informational culture, digital educational environment, future teachers, digital technologies, digital competencies, critical thinking skills.

INTRODUCTION

The second half of the XXth century, as a period of development of fast, large-scale information system and telecommunications technologies, is recognized as the penetration of almost all aspects of life and human activities, as well as the globalization of the information space, a factor that has influenced and is showing the development of the whole world. A notable aspect is the enormous increase in the need of people for active information exchange within the country and in the outside world. The development of the information sphere with such speed, the growth of its potential and capabilities, its wide use in various directions of public and state life can be one of the important factors that determine the development of humanity in the new XIst century.

In our country, too, the informatization of society is established by law. Article 4 of the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "on informatization" clearly defines the state policy in the field of informatization. According to him, public policy in the field of informatization is aimed at creating a national Information System, taking into account the modern world principles of development and improvement of Information Resources, Information Technology and Information Systems.

The main directions of public policy in the field of informatization are as follows: implementation of the constitutional rights of everyone to free access and dissemination of information, ensuring the free use of information resources;

creation of a unified information space based on information systems of state bodies, network and territorial information systems, as well as information systems of legal entities and individuals;
creating conditions for the free use of international information networks and the Internet world Information Network;
formation of State Information Resources, creation and development of information systems, ensuring their compatibility and interaction;
Organization of the production of modern means of Information Technology;
assistance in the formation of the information resources, services and Information Technology Market;
promote the development of the production of software products;
support and promotion of entrepreneurship, creating favorable conditions for attracting investments;
it consists in training personnel and improving their skills, stimulating scientific research¹.

Article 13 of the law "on the principles and guarantees of freedom of information" sets out the safety of an individual in the field of information, the safety of an individual in the field of information is ensured by creating the necessary conditions and guarantees of his free use of information, keeping secrets relating to his personal life, protecting against illegal mental

Based on the analysis of foreign experiments on the provision of Information Security, a specific legislative system for the prevention, elimination and fight against unhealthy information flows in a number of developed countries is evidenced. Examples include the convention on cybercrime in international practice in this regard, the recommendations of the Assembly of the European Union Parliament "on the introduction of Safe Internet and online resources for minors", the German law "on the protection of students", the Lithuanian law "on the protection of minors from the negative effects of mass information" and the Russian law "on the protection of children.

In the United States, the 1998 law embodied the norms governing the protection of children under the age of Seventeen from the negative effects of the internet in the process of physical and mental development (Child Online Protection Act). This law provided for the issues of responsibility for posting and distributing pictures, images, graphs, audiomaterials, video files on the internet, which are harmful to minors. Alternatively, the law established that parents,

¹ Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, K.A. The time of personality and the time of life. – St. Petersburg: Aleteya, 2001. – p. 304.

caregivers, industry representatives are obliged to protect minors from negative information on the internet. The specific aspect of the act was that a provisional Commission of 17 members was outlined, which would be formed by House of Representatives Spekiri and a majority of Senate leaders. The members of the commission were established to coordinate activities that reduce the impact of harmful information on the use of the internet in the educational process of minors as a function of the commission, consisting of representatives of business in the field of the Internet².

The Act, which came into force in 2001, mandated that all public institutions receiving state dotasias install a content filtration system (Child Internet Protection Act). At the moment, a special norm has been introduced into the relevant legislation on the obligation of providers to impose a barrier on networks where information related to child pornography is located³.

A new law, "Loppsi-2", passed in France, gave the state the right to regulate the internet, to monitor the use of the internet. According to it, all information about internet access will now be sent to the national database. In some European countries, the ban on sites with negative content is established on the basis of the law. In Germany, for example, this issue is carried out on the basis of a court decision. In Russia, a "safe Internet Center" was established in order to combat various information attacks. The EU has also adopted 6 legislation and developed a secure Internet program⁴.

In a globalizing world, information is of great importance in inter-people and interstate relations. That is, it can manifest itself as both a positive and a negative force in the life of the world community. In this sense, countries with great potential in the technical and technological sphere will have favorable conditions. It is thanks to this advantage that they can and are pushing forward values, points of view, ideas, opinions that are in their personal interests. Accordingly, anti-globalization movements are taking place in many states, which refuse to form a single World-harmonized information space. At this point, it is worth noting that the anti-globalization movement itself is increasingly taking on a global action tone. Such information, which travels on a global scale, does not affect the interests of a particular state. Not only is it able

² 105th Congress Report House of Representatives 2d Session 105 775 Child online protection act October 5, 1998.

³ Dawn S. Conrad, Note, Protecting Children from Pornography on the Internet: Freedom of Speech is Pitching and Congress May Strike Out, 9 RICH. J.L. & TECH. 2 (Winter 2002), at <http://jolt.richmond.edu/v9i2/Note.html>.

⁴ Badalov.M. A journal of life-giving ideas // law and duty in the minds of young people. - T., 2014. - №6. // www.huquqburch.uz.

to testify to the social, political and processes in a particular country where this information is disseminated, but it also affects the interests of this country, as the audience of other countries, which has not said anything about these messages, compares them to the state in their state. For this reason, some disagreements between the states, the khukumats, can occasionally come to the surface. It is not always easy to determine who is right or who is wrong in this.

As a result of the development of fast information and communication technologies, the world is living on the basis of various ideological threats that can negatively affect the morale of all mankind, including our people, at a time when globalization processes are taking place among different peoples and elates.

The mind of students who are always interested in the news, various information, is imbued with a huge meaning in every thought point that is being said about the extent to which the Internet affects. Some disruptors who are well aware of the students ' Internet interests are taking great advantage of this and escalating the "information attack".

But it cannot be overlooked that such achievements, a high and bright manifestation of human thought, are also used as an ideological weapon in the implementation of the ulterior motives of certain political forces, which at the same time have great power and financial capabilities. Understanding the true nature of such attempts to derail the mind and thinking, the spiritual world of people, primarily young people, their long and lasting, negative consequences and the Prevention of such risks are becoming extremely important today".

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, during the years of independence, the legal framework for ensuring information security was created and special attention is paid to improving the issue in connection with its relevance. This, in turn, requires the development of competency in ensuring information security in students.

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